

1 **Title: The mechanical effect of monitoring and controlling the**
2 **impregnation in the resin infusion process**

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8 **Abstract:**

9 Nowadays, most of industries are optimizing their processes to make their products more
10 competitive. In the composites manufacturing industry, there is a big gap between the almost
11 fully automated processes and those which require an intensive labor-work. Although it has
12 many advantages, the resin infusion (RI) process is characterized for its lack of automation.
13 As a consequence, the results are strongly dependent on the process boundaries, the operator
14 skills and expertise, and the result is usually far away from the optimum. In this work, the
15 application of a novel methodology and its capability to maximize the mechanical properties
16 of infusion-manufactured composite materials is presented. After manufacturing stitched and
17 unstitched materials at different impregnation velocities, an optimum value was assessed.
18 The application of this value during the manufacture has increased the tensile and impact
19 properties.

20 **Keywords:** composite, control, mechanical properties, impact, tensile, voids.

21

22 **1. Introduction**

23 Nowadays, composite materials are becoming more popular in some sectors such as the
24 automotive or sports due to their high specific mechanical properties. Weight saving is one
25 of the most important goals for composite-based products and the light-weight manufacturing
26 can reduce the costs [1] and weight up to 40% [2]. The higher mechanical performance of
27 the material, the lower material amount is required. Then, achieving the maximum
28 mechanical properties is a must to minimize the weight, the waste and optimize the resources.
29 The process automation is a base to fulfill these objectives [3].

30 Most of composite manufacturing processes require a great effort of dry fiber handling
31 and processing [4]. Many ideas have been proposed to deal with the challenge of its
32 automation. Main efforts have been done in robotics, mainly to manage the dry fibers [5], [6]
33 and automate the manufacturing of large parts [7]. Also, many experiences have also been
34 focused on curing control [8]. Nevertheless, other stages of the process have not been deeply
35 automated, such as the impregnation, also known as infiltration. Only limited literature is
36 found in this area, specifically in the case of active control. In particular, Alms et al. [9]
37 proposed a system to control the resin flow by modifying the mold external pressure and
38 Sozer et al. [10] and Devillard et al. [11] analyzed the flow and corrected some undesirable
39 disturbances in real time. As reviewed by Seyednouran [12], these techniques usually entail
40 extensive and complex tooling. In this respect, this work tries to avoid these drawbacks by
41 using a conventional mold and cost-effective methods.

42 Several manufacturing processes are available to produce continuous-fiber reinforced
43 polymers, as reviewed by Rajak et al, [13]. LCM (liquid composited molding) techniques,
44 such as RTM (resin transfer molding) and RFI (resin film infusion) or simply RI (resin
45 infusion), are based on the impregnation of an initially dry fibers in the interior of a mold
46 cavity. LCM techniques are widely used in the automotive and energy industries [4] as well
47 as in some specific parts for aerospace applications [7]. Resin Infusion process is the
48 preferred production method for large composite parts such as wind turbine blades, aircraft
49 wing covers or boats. Nevertheless, RI processes show some reliability and repeatability
50 challenges, mainly related with the impregnation quality and the intensive hand-work
51 required. RTM uses a double-side rigid mold, and positive pressure is applied to force the
52 resin to flow through the fibers, before reaching the vent port at the atmospheric pressure. In
53 RI, one mold side is replaced by a flexible and airtight bag, and the applied differential
54 pressure at the mold ports is generated only by a vacuum pump. The vacuum pump is plugged
55 into one port, while the other port is connected to a resin pot at atmospheric pressure. It
56 induces a flow movement and the impregnation through the defined path from the pot port(s)
57 to the vacuum port(s) is performed. As the flow goes further, the pressure gradient is getting
58 lower, as the applied pressure keeps constant and the impregnated length is increasing.
59 Consequently, the impregnation velocity (i.e. flow front velocity) is getting lower as the flow

60 front goes further. It can be modelled by the Darcy's model for porous media [14], as shown
61 in Eq. 1 for the unidimensional case, where u is the flow front velocity, ΔP is the applied
62 differential pressure, Δx is the impregnated distance, K is the unidimensional permeability
63 factor, μ is the dynamic viscosity and \emptyset is the porosity.

$$u = \frac{\Delta P \cdot K}{\Delta x \cdot \mu \cdot \emptyset} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

64 Eq. 1, which is dependent of the flow position, can be rewritten as a function of the process
65 time, Δt (Eq. 2).

$$u = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta P \cdot K}{\Delta t \cdot \mu \cdot \emptyset}} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

66 As a consequence of the pressure gradient variation, while the rest of parameters in Eq. 1
67 and Eq. 2 are presumably constant, the velocity u is proportional to Δx^{-1} or $\Delta t^{-1/2}$. It means
68 that very high velocities are induced at the beginning of the impregnation process, while low
69 velocities can be expected at the end of the impregnation process. As a result, a non-
70 homogeneous velocity pattern is produced in the laminate, which has negative effect in the
71 material performance. The variation in the impregnation velocity has been reported as one of
72 the main factors which generate internal defects in the final material [15]. This non-
73 homogeneous velocity may change the impregnation performance and the defects generation
74 phenomena, especially in dual-scale laminates, as it has been often reported [16].
75 Structurally, dry fiber reinforcements are usually arranged as dual-scale preforms, where
76 empty spaces can be found at different locations. Micro-gaps are located among individual
77 fibers, as macro-gaps are located among individual yarns. When the resin is forced to flow
78 within the fibers and yarns, two phenomena drive the process. On the one hand, the applied
79 external pressure induces a macro-flow going through macro-gaps as the lowest pressure
80 losses are found there. This macro-flow is dominated by the viscous forces. On the other
81 hand, due to the small scale of the micro-gaps, a noticeable capillary effect is also induced
82 [17]. During the impregnation process, if one of these two flows is going faster than the
83 another, the slowest one will have no time to fill their gaps completely. Consequently, voids
84 are generated. When capillary phenomenon is dominating the impregnation, macrovoids are
85 generated within the yarns. Otherwise, when the macro-flow is the fastest one, microvoids
86 are generated within the individual fibers. Then, there is an intermediate value for the flow
87 rate which minimizes both undesired phenomena [18] and the minimum void content will be
88 obtained, as described by the V-shape curve in the work of Causse et al [19].

89 Many works have reported the negative effect of voids over the mechanical performance
90 of composites for in-plane and out-of-plane loads [16], [20]. Specifically, authors such as

91 Leclerc et al. [21] and Olivero et al. [22] show reductions in the in-plane tensile properties
92 when the void content is increased. Similarly, Patou et al. [23] reported a reduction in the
93 out-of-plane impact properties as a consequence of voids presence. Also, the absorbed energy
94 (i.e. damage) during the impact was higher in case of higher void content, as reviewed by
95 Mehdikhani et al. [16]. In RTM, optimum velocity and pressure which maximize the
96 mechanical properties were found [21], [24]. No related works are available in the literature
97 for RI processes. In this study, low-velocity impact and tensile test have been chosen as
98 representative tests to cover both in-plane and out-of-plane loads.

99 In this context, the initially proposed idea of Trochu et al. [25] of keeping the flow front
100 velocity close to the optimal conditions in RTM is interesting, although it shows some
101 uncovered challenges. As described by Causse et al, [19] and Leclerc and Ruiz [21], imposing
102 a flow profile requires from the fiber/resin system characterization. Even when this
103 characterization is done for each specific laminate, the application is not simple, especially
104 in RI, where the flow rate is depending on the pressure throughout many variables. For
105 complex geometries, corrections were successfully carried out by Causse et al. [19] in RTM,
106 where the flow rate can be easily controlled. For RI, it implies an additional complexity in
107 the setup, since the relationship between the velocity and the applied pressure gradient should
108 be also characterized. Among the very limited literature, recently, He et al. [26] have used a
109 real-time flow control system to minimize the void content in LCM processes, and noticeable
110 improvements were reported.

111 To control the flow front velocity, the flow position should be firstly accurately measured.
112 Some techniques have been proposed in the literature to track the flow front position. Di
113 Fratta et al. [27] and Endruweit et al., [28] used pressure sensors embedded in the mold,
114 although no further control was done. Optic fiber sensors were used by Ahn and Lee [29], as
115 well as ultrasound sensors and resistive sensors, used by He et al. [26]. Most of these
116 techniques are usually used as a single point methods and the reported information could be
117 limited. Optical methods have also been used during the impregnation or permeability
118 measurements, as reviewed by Grössing and coworkers [30] and recently for Geng et al. [31].
119 Nevertheless, as reported by Vernet et al., [32], the image processing is not applied at real
120 time and subsequent image analysis is performed afterwards. Major difficulties in the flow
121 controlling can be observed when complex laminates are impregnated. As permeability
122 manages the flow behaviour, according to the Darcy's model, laminates with non-
123 homogeneous fibre distribution or reinforcements could make the flow control more difficult
124 [33]. In this respect, stitching, as a three-dimensional reinforcement [34], changes the flow
125 behaviour, the defects generation and flow distribution could be unpredictable [35]. In this
126 context, computerized vision, as a full field technique, allows to monitor the whole flow front
127 in real time, whatever geometry or laminate is used.

128 Then, a novel cost-effective approach is proposed in this work for RI applications. It is
129 based on a real time controller that is continuously monitoring and controlling the
130 instantaneous flow front velocity according to the pre-defined optimum velocity goal. It
131 allows keeping a constant and optimum flow front velocity during the whole impregnation
132 process. The main advantage of this system is that the permeability distribution and the flow
133 behaviour could remain unknown during the process, although the process is done at
134 optimum values.

135 **2. Experimental**

136 To optimize the mechanical properties of RI manufactured composites, a novel
137 manufacturing control approach is presented. Based on the relationship between the
138 impregnation velocity and the mechanical properties, the flow front velocity is measured and
139 controlled using a developed computer vision system.

140 *2.1. Measuring and controlling the impregnation*

141 As described by Eq. 1 and Eq. 2, the applied pressure should be modified continuously as
142 a function of the time, t , or the flow position, Δx , to keep the velocity constant at optimum
143 value. The proposed method to perform this work is schematically presented in the Figure 1.
144 In the first stage, the unknown material should be characterized. Mechanical tests are carried
145 out for materials manufactured at different impregnation velocities in simple geometries.
146 Optimum velocity can be assessed from these analyses. To manufacture materials with
147 optimum properties, this previously calculated optimum velocity is given as an input in the
148 algorithm. The algorithm reads the camera images, which is continuously taking pictures of
149 the laminate. Using computer vision techniques, these images are processed in real time to
150 detect the flow position and then, the instantaneous velocity can be calculated taking into
151 account the processing framerate. The actual velocity is compared with the optimum velocity
152 and then, the difference (i.e. error) is calculated. A proportional output signal is given to the
153 adjustable valve as input. This valve manages the flowrate going inside the mold. Only in the
154 case that the actual velocity is equal to the optimum, the valve position does not change.
155 Otherwise, the valve is opened or closed as per the algorithm's output.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the adopted methodology.

156 The setup of this concept is shown in Figure 2a. Once the mold is properly sealed after
 157 dry fiber placement, one port is connected to the resin pot. The other port is connected to the
 158 controlled valve, which is subsequently connected to the vacuum pump. A camera is located
 159 at the top of the mold to record the flow front during the impregnation process. The camera
 160 is continuously taking images of the laminate and they are processed in a computer in real
 161 time (Figure 2b). Depending on the actual flow velocity, the valve is accordingly adjusted,
 162 after comparing the value with the optimum. The system is surrounded by an opaque box to
 163 avoid the influence of any external light, as it increases the robustness of the process. To
 164 process the images, an initial picture is taken before starting the process, which is set as the
 165 reference image. Then, when the process starts, images are taken at 10 frames per second and
 166 the reference image is subtracted pixel by pixel. As a result, the impregnated and
 167 unimpregnated area are clearly highlighted. Then, it is analyzed using computer vision
 168 techniques. Gradient-based operators are used to isolate the flow front at each taken picture.
 169 Once the flow front position is known, the velocity can be evaluated when consecutive
 170 images are analyzed. This instantaneous velocity is compared with the optimum value which
 171 was preliminary set in the controller for the specific material. According to the difference,
 172 the signal is proportionally applied on the valve to modify the resin flow rate to keep it in the
 173 optimum value.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. (a) Setup to impregnate the fabrics using a real-time velocity controller, and (b) example of camera pictures of flow front at two different times.

174 *2.2. Equipment and materials*

175 In addition to the previously introduced controlling system, other equipment and materials
 176 have been used to manufacture and test the specimens. A $900 \times 700 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ steel plate was
 177 used as a mold to manufacture all plate-shaped specimens. A wood box of $900 \times 900 \times 500 \text{ mm}^3$
 178 has been used to isolate the setup from the external light conditions. As a matrix, a polyester-
 179 based system P4 TV-28 (DSM, Germany) has been used and catalyzed with M312 (Curox,
 180 Germany) at 2% weight. As a reinforcement, unidirectional 600 g/m^2 E-glass fiber plies were
 181 used. To build the airtight bag, a $75 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ BF-32 (Airtech Inc, US) nylon bag was sealed using
 182 AT200Y tape (Airtech Inc, US). Vacuum was applied with an Edwards 80 pump (Edwards

183 Vacuum, UK). Stitching was performed using a Pffaf 3574 sewing machine with computer
184 numerical control (CNC), available in the Leibniz Institute for Composite Materials,
185 (Kaiserslautern, Germany) and Saba C50 thread (Amann & Sohne GmbH, Germany) was
186 used. To measure the flow front position during the impregnation, a monochrome Mako 130B
187 camera (Allied Vision, Germany) was used.

188 Finally, to perform the mechanical tensile test, a MTS 370.02 (MTS Systems Corporation,
189 US) servohydraulic machine has been used. For impact tests, two drop towers have been
190 employed. One, with 15 m height, is available in the Leibniz Institute for Composite
191 Materials, (Kaiserslautern, Germany) while the another with 2 m is set at the University of
192 Jaén (Spain). A hemispherical Ø16 mm impactor was set in both devices. Impactor position
193 was continuously monitored using Digital Image Correlation. A high-speed camera was used
194 to capture the images of the impact event. After that, a commercial solution (VIC-2D,
195 Correlated Solutions, Irmo, SC, USA) was used to track the speckle pattern and calculate the
196 position and the velocity during the impact. To analyze the damage of the impacted
197 specimens, a backlight system has been used, as the change in the light transmission trough
198 the thickness highlights the affected area, as other studies have reported [36].

199 *2.3. Manufacturing and testing*

200 To analyze the effect of controlling the impregnation velocity, different laminates were
201 manufactured and tested under tensile and low-velocity impact tests. Tensile specimens were
202 manufactured at different fibre orientation, as shown in Figure 3, where the arrow means the
203 load application in tensile test. The orientation was changed by modifying the relative angle
204 between the flow direction and the fiber orientation. Consequently, specimens were also cut
205 perpendicularly to the flow front, aiming to minimize the flow variations along the size of
206 the specimens. Three specimens were cut from each laminate and five laminates were
207 manufactured at each orientation. For impact laminates, the target velocities were set constant
208 for each laminate: 2.5 mm/s, 4.0 mm/s, 6.0 mm/s and 11.0 mm/s for unstitched laminates.
209 For stitched laminates, slightly higher values were set, as they show higher permeabilities.
210 Five specimens were manufactured at each velocity. Stitching was performed using a grid
211 with 3.33 mm between stitches and 10 mm between seams in a squared distribution. One-
212 side lock-stitch configuration was adopted.

Figure 3. Specimens impregnation for tensile tests.

213 Subsequently, mechanical tests were performed. Firstly, tensile tests were carried out
 214 according to ASTM D3039 [37]. Optimum flow front velocity was calculated from these
 215 results, and the impregnation and tests were repeated using this value. Then, impact tests
 216 were performed according to ASTM D7136/7136M [38] using 13 J of impact energy, and
 217 then, 26 J was applied over the same specimens. The setup for the impact tests is shown in
 218 Figure 4, where the specimen's center was perpendicular and vertically aligned with the
 219 impactor axis. Digital image correlation technique (DIC) was used to measure the actual
 220 impactor velocity and displacement during the event, so speckle was added to the mobile
 221 frame. As a consequence of the high frame rate, an extra power light was required.

Figure 4. Set-up for impact tests, using a DIC system to measure the impactor position.

222 Then, the absorbed energy by the specimen was assessed using the Eq. 3, where E_a is the
223 absorbed energy at time t , m is the mobile frame mass, v_i is the initial impactor velocity at
224 the point of impact, $v(t)$ is the impactor velocity at time t , g is the acceleration due to gravity,
225 and $\delta(t)$ is the impactor displacement at time t .

$$E_a = \frac{m \cdot (v_i^2 - v(t)^2)}{2} + m \cdot g \cdot \delta(t) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

226 3. Results and discussion

227 3.1. Tensile tests

228 In the first experiment, different fibre orientations were impregnated without control
229 system. The goal of this experiment was to evaluate the real impregnation velocity at the
230 position where specimens were cut. As the specimens were distributed along the flow path,
231 specimens manufactured at different velocities were collected. Also, the algorithm was tested
232 for the different fiber arrangements and permeabilities. As expected, the flow-aligned (i.e.
233 [0₂]) configuration shows the shortest impregnation time (34.0 s) and the highest
234 impregnation velocities. Moreover, the cross-flow oriented configuration shows the lowest
235 impregnation time (46.3 s) as well as the lowest impregnation velocities. The permeability
236 values of each case are behind these differences. After manufacturing, the specimens were
237 cut and tensile tests were performed.

238 Figure 5 shows the results of tensile test for the three different fiber orientations. Tensile
239 modulus and tensile strength have been plotted as a function of the impregnation velocity.
240 Although a high dispersion is observed in the experimental data, significant differences are
241 reported when intermediate velocity values are compared with high and low values. Values
242 have been adjusted by a straight line in the x-log plot, as also other authors did [19]. The
243 highest values can be found in the range from 2 mm/s to 6 mm/s, where the three tested fiber
244 orientations report their maximums. At 0°, the mean value of tensile strength in this range
245 was 233 ± 46 MPa while the mean of all specimens was 191.4 ± 42.5 MPa, which means an
246 increase of 21.7 %. Similarly, increases of 13.2% and 12.0% was measured at 45° and 90°,
247 respectively. For tensile modulus, increases of 5.5%, 8.3% and 7.4% was measured for fibers
248 at 0°, 45 and 90°, respectively. The less sensitive orientation was 0° since this case is the less
249 sensitive to matrix properties, as highlighted in the revision of Mehdikhani et al. [16]. It
250 should be highlighted that in all cases, tensile modulus and tensile strength are higher than
251 the mean in the range of the considered optimum values. Indeed, the relative increase in
252 strength is higher than the modulus. It can be explained when the voids in the material are
253 considered as stress raisers. Since the volume of the microvoids and macrovoids is relatively

254 small, the effect in the cross sectional area is limited and the modulus does not change
 255 noticeably. Nevertheless, the tensile stress at the voids surface is noticeably higher than the
 256 mean stress and the breakage is reached before the corresponding yield point without voids.

Figure 5. Tensile modulus (top) and strength (bottom) at different fibre orientations show intermediate optimum values.

257 *3.2. Impact tests*

258 Firstly, unstitched [0₂,90₂]_s specimens were impacted at 13 ± 0.1 J, and after at 26 ± 0.2 J.
 259 The results are shown in Figure 6 where the two energies have been plotted once the signal
 260 filtering is applied to remove the random vibration noise. At 13 J, all results are very
 261 repetitive among all specimens impregnated at the same velocity, where the mean standard
 262 deviation is lower than 0.6%. The maximum values were obtained at 6.0 mm/s (3999 ± 16
 263 N). The values in the range from 4 mm/s to 6 mm/s are only 1.9% higher than those out of
 264 this range (maximum of 3999 ± 16 N was obtained at 6.0 mm/s). At 26 J, the differences are
 265 more noticeable. The mean value in the range from 4 mm/s to 6 mm/s (dashed square) is
 266 6499 ± 290 N, while the mean value out of this range was 5794 ± 526 N which represents an
 267 increase of 12.2%. These values are within the ranges shown by other authors, as reviewed
 268 by Mehdikhani et al. [16] for impact loads when voids are present.

Figure 6. Impactor peak force at the tested flow front velocities for unstitched laminates. Specimens were impacted at 13 J and reimpacted at 26 J.

269 The same tests were performed with stitched and unstitched [90₂,0]_S laminates. The
 270 maximum peak force at the impactor is shown in Figure 7 for the different impregnation
 271 velocities. Optimum values have been found in the range from 5 mm/s to 7.5 mm/s (dashed
 272 rectangle). According to the results of the optimum range, the increase in the impact force is
 273 3.9 % and 3.1 % for impact at 26 J and 13 J respectively. In all cases, the effect of velocity
 274 optimization is more limited in the case of stitched laminates. In these cases, the effect of
 275 stitching masks the effect of the velocity optimization. Indeed, the increase associated to
 276 stitching, according to Figure 7 is 9.7% and 6.4%, which is much higher than the increase by
 277 the velocity optimization. Then, because of the intrinsic effect of stitching, the mechanical
 278 performance of the stitched laminates is higher than the unstitched ones, even when those
 279 have been impregnated at optimized velocities.

Figure 7. Impactor peak force at the tested flow front velocities for stitched and unstitched laminates, impacted at 13 J and reimpacted at 26 J.

280 The tracking of the impactor (Figure 8a) allows calculating the impactor position and
 281 velocity (Figure 8b), and the absorbed energy was evaluated (Figure 8c).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 8. (a) Impactor position sequence, (b) impactor displacement and velocity data and (c) impactor dissipated energy during one impact event.

282 The absorbed energy in the specimens has been plotted in Figure 9. As a result, no
 283 remarkable differences have been observed in the case of low energy impacts, where only
 284 the unstitched laminate and the stitched which was impregnated at the highest velocity shows
 285 a slight increment. Then, the stitching and the velocity optimization have a not very relevant
 286 effect at low energies. At 13 J, the measured energy was 6.4 J for the specimens manufactured
 287 at 2.5 mm/s, 5.0 mm/s and 7.5 mm/s, and 7.0 J for the specimen manufactured at 13.5 mm/s.
 288 Also, 7.5 J were measured in the case of unstitched laminate manufactured at 5.5 mm/s. It
 289 means that the optimized laminates show reductions up to 8.6 % of absorbed energy while
 290 adding stitching shows reductions up to 14.6%. On the other hand, at 26 J, higher differences
 291 are concluded. At 26 J, the measured energies were 18.8 J, 15.6 J, 17.9 J and 19.3 J for
 292 specimens manufactured at 2.5 mm/s, 5.0 mm/s, 7.5 mm/s and 13.5 mm/s respectively. Also,
 293 20.6 J was measured for the specimen manufactured at 5.5 mm/s. It means that velocity
 294 optimization can decrease the absorbed energy up to 19.2% while adding stitching shows
 295 reductions up to 24.3%, as damaged area is smaller in both cases.

296 Summarizing, the unstitched laminates show the highest absorbed energy due to extended
 297 damage has been generated as delaminations. Specimens impacted at low energy have
 298 absorbed roughly the same energy. At high energy, the effect of optimized impregnation is
 299 remarkable, and the best results have been reported at 5 mm/s. The farther away from the
 300 optimum value, the higher absorbed energy in form of damage. This optimum value is

301 slightly higher than the optimum values for tensile tests. Consequently, a more negative effect
 302 of macrovoids is reported for impact loads. It means that macrovoids and microvoids have a
 303 different impact on mechanical properties, as was also reported by [21].

Figure 9. Absorbed energy in the range of analyzed velocities at the two energy levels, for stitched and unstitched laminates.

304 To explain these differences, the damage has been analyzed. Figure 10 shows the backlight
 305 images of both types of specimens after 26 J re-impacts in which clearer areas mean highly
 306 damaged areas. Figure 10a shows an unstitched laminate which was impregnated at high
 307 velocity. Figure 10b shows the configuration impregnated at the optimum velocity, and
 308 damage has been clearly reduced and concentrated around the impact point. Figure 10c shows
 309 a stitched configuration which was impregnated at high velocity while Figure 10d
 310 corresponds to the optimized impregnation. When both unstitched are compared, the
 311 optimized one shows a more concentrated damage with shorter propagation distances. The
 312 same can be observed for the stitched laminates. When the unstitched and stitched are
 313 compared, it can be concluded that the stitching is very effective as it can limit the damage
 314 propagation. Once stitching is included, the damage is mainly propagated along the seam
 315 lines as stitches work as stress raisers and cracks find the propagation easier along these weak
 316 points. Stitching is avoiding the extensive propagation of the delaminations. In the unstitched,
 317 instead, the damage is not restrained and large delaminated areas are observed. Then,
 318 stitching has modified the primary fracture mechanism from large interlaminar delaminations
 319 to crack propagation through the seams.

Figure 10. Damage backlight images of specimens after the 26 J re-impacts. (a) Unstitched and unoptimized, (b) unstitched and optimized; (c) stitched unoptimized and (d) stitched and optimized.

320 The effect of stitching can also be noticed when a cross-sectional view at the damaged
 321 area is analyzed. Figure 11 shows a comparative images of unstitched and stitched laminates
 322 after being impacted. Extended delaminations have been observed in the unstitched laminates
 323 (Figure 11a), where no links are present to keep consecutive plies together when shear stress
 324 is generated at the interface. It promotes large delaminations through the interfaces. On the
 325 other hand, stitching has avoided the delamination from be extensively propagated (Figure
 326 11b). Nevertheless, large voids (i.e. macrovoids) have been observed near the stitching points
 327 as a consequence of the yarn distortions because of the transversal stitches. In both cases,
 328 macrovoids have been observed in the internal plies. As a result, stitching changes the
 329 damage mechanism for impact loads as delaminations are avoided while crack propagation
 330 through the seams are promoted. Despite of these two opposite effects of stitching, taking
 331 into account the mechanical results of impact force and absorbed energy, the impact
 332 behaviour has been enhanced by using stitching.

Figure 11. Cross sectional views after 26 J impacts. (a) Unstitched laminate, where large delaminations have been observed; and (b) stitched laminate where delaminations have been avoided by the stitching linking effects, although macrovoids are shown near the stitching points at the mold face.

333 5. Conclusions

334 In this work, the application of control system in composites manufacturing has been
 335 successfully applied in the RI process. The tensile and impact properties have been improved
 336 in unstitched and stitched laminates.

337 Both tensile and impact tests have reported optimum impregnation velocities in the range
 338 from 2.5 mm/s to 8.0 mm/s. In this range, slightly higher values have been observed in the
 339 case of impact properties, that means that the mechanical effect of microvoids and
 340 macrovoids are different within the type of load. Non-significant differences have been
 341 observed in the optimum flow front velocity as a function of the fibre orientation. Further
 342 experimental tests may clarify this relation.

343 The application of the flow front controller is highly effective for high energy impacts,
 344 while only slight improvements have been reported at low energy impacts. Similarly,
 345 stitching is specifically effective at high-energy impacts, where the extension of the
 346 delaminations are restrained and limited. The impregnation velocity in stitched laminates can
 347 also be optimized. Similar ranges for the optimums have been reported. It means that the
 348 presented methodology can be successfully used in complex laminates manufacturing by RI.

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